

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 63.4078 Max: 63.6958	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1174 ☐ Natural ☒ Anthropic	Gabil Project
				In cross-section? ☐ Yes ☒ No	In elevation drawing? ☐ Yes ☒ No	
DEFINITION FILL OF CONSTRUCTION CUT OF WALL 1058				Covered by SU: 1010	Fills ☒ SU: 1175	Filled by SU:
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? ☐ Color ☒ Composition ☐ Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS ☐ Accumulation ☒ Construction ☐ Cutting ☐ Erosion ☐ Collapse ☐ Intentional deposition			
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are					SOIL/MATRIX clay ___% silt ___% sand ___% ☐ Granular ☐ Layered ☐ Cohesive	
Anthropic		Geological		Organic		
☒ Pottery ☐ Nails ☒ Tiles ☐ Marble ☐ Amphorae ☐ Quarried debris ☐ Dolia ☐ Slag ☐ Brick ☐ Mosaic tile(s) ☐ Basalt slabs ☐ Mortar ☐ Opus signinum ☐ Coins ☐ Painted plaster ☐ Metal (specify) ☐ Burnt Adobe ☐ Collapse debris ☐ Other (specify) ☐ Glass		☒ Tufo (specify) Bedrock and tufo slabs ☒ Travertine ☐ Other Limestone ☐ Basalt ☐ Clay ☐ Sand ☐ Silt ☐ Pebbles (range) ☐ Gravel (range)		☒ Charcoal ☐ Ash ☒ Animal bones ☐ Human bones ☐ Animal teeth ☐ Human teeth ☒ Shells ☐ Other (specify)		
					Compaction: ☐ Hard ☒ Compact ☐ Friable ☐ Loose ☐ Soft Color: ☐ Black ☐ Brown ☒ Gray ☐ Light Brown ☐ Light Gray ☐ White ☐ Yellow ☐ Red ☐ Light Yellow ☐ Other (specify)	
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)						
Northern Limit		☐ Original ☐ Not Original		☒ Excavation Limit		Depth: ☐ Original ☒ Not Original
Southern Limit		☒ Original ☐ Not Original		☒ Excavation Limit		
Western Limit		☒ Original ☐ Not Original		☐ Excavation Limit		
Eastern Limit		☒ Original ☐ Not Original		☐ Excavation Limit		
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE						
Is equal to:			Is bound to (only for masonry):			
Is abutted by:			Abuts: SU 1135			
Is covered by: 1016			Covers:			
Is cut by:			Cuts:			
Is filled by:			Fills: SU 1175			
OBSERVATIONS The fill follows the line of wall SU 1058; and appears to correspond to wall SU 1162 although their relationship is not yet clear. Wall slabs at the southern most end of fill rest to 1162.						
DESCRIPTION Position within sector: SW corner of Area B Shape: rectilinear shape, follows the line of wall SU 1058						
For layers complete this section: Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): slopes down to south w/ the natural surface of the area Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): Rubble fill Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): thickness is consistent, but at 5 meters seems to be composed of Nature of the interface with layer below: ☐ sharp ☐ diffuse ☒ commingled ☐ other (specify) bedrock rather than rubble						
For cuts complete this section: Cut edges: ☐ rounded ☐ straight Cut sides: ☐ straight ☐ concave ☐ convex ☐ sloping Cut bottom: ☐ flat ☐ concave ☐ irregular How is cut top edge? ☐ sharp ☐ rounded How is cut bottom edge? ☐ sharp ☐ rounded Observations:			Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North): from side Length 5.75m Width 0.77m View from above ← N Bed rock Wall SU 1058 Curved featu			

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

^{not}
 The fill is definitely related to tufo wall SU 105B. It is not yet clear whether 105B acts as a retaining wall for a wall of the same nature and composition as SU 116Z or if the fill represents the construction cut for wall 105B (it doesn't).
 The composition of the fill changes from rubble to bedrock at circa 5m but this change cannot be explained without further excavation. Further excavation demonstrates ~~as~~ an ash has recycled ashlar wall blocks at the bottom of the fill abutting SU 116Z. At this level travertine blocks could also be found projecting from SU 1169 - the easternmost edge of the cut cut 1175

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

(*) D. Francis; M. Pry 20-07-10

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by	Megan Goldman-Peterson	on	14/07/10
Revised by	CMM	on	20/07/2010
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